

TEACHING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS HOW TO WORK WITH WORK TOOLS IN TECHNOLOGY CLASSES, INTRODUCING THEM TO THE RULES OF SAFETY, AND GIVING THEM AN UNDERSTANDING

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ABSTRACT: *In this article, elementary school students are given concepts about the correct and careful use of work tools in technology lessons, and some practical work processes are highlighted. Methods of teaching safety rules were mentioned by the teachers. The practical importance of technological science and its role in the system are discussed.*

KEY WORDS: *Concept, recommendation, global, technique, technology, practice, working tools, security, law, methodology, method, direction.*

Technology classes are one of the interesting subjects for elementary school students of general secondary schools. Technology science has an important place in the proper organization of the educational process for the all-round maturity of the young generation among many subjects. The knowledge and skills acquired from the subject of "Technology" will definitely be useful in life, no matter what profession the student takes when he grows up. Today, technology serves as the main helper and important resource for young people in choosing a profession, becoming a well-rounded person, and developing their creative abilities. Technology lessons bring joy to students. Because in this lesson, they see the pleasure of their work, they enjoy what they have done, which in turn helps to form a number of positive feelings in students. In technology lessons, the scope of students' knowledge expands, their respect for work increases, and their interest in the profession is awakened. In order for these processes to happen, the teacher needs to organize the lesson effectively and thoroughly prepare for each lesson. There are many ways to achieve efficiency and increase students' interest in technology lessons. Let's get acquainted with some of them below. Trips organized in technology lessons - depending on the topic of the lesson, with the permission of the head of the school, trips can be organized during the course of the lesson or during free time from the lesson. Together with students, going to national craft houses, museums, to craftsmen and carpenters with many years of experience, watching their handiwork, getting to know the technology of preparation gives them a

special pleasure. During trips organized in technology classes, students get acquainted with many professions related to carpentry, plumbing, tailoring and cooking. This will increase students' interest in acquiring one of these professions in their future life and becoming skilled specialists in the field. Organizing "master-classes" in technology lessons - inviting craftsmen, carpenters, tailors and other professionals with many years of experience to the lesson process. Sharing their life experience. It will be an unforgettable process and experience for students to get answers to their interesting questions and to perform certain labor activities together with them.

As a result, students remember the work experience learned from them in technology classes and test themselves in practical classes. The use of ICT in the course of technology education is now impossible to imagine any field without ICT. Although technology lessons are based on practical work processes, the effective use of information technologies helps the successful passage of the lesson process. Elementary school students learn to make various flowers, models, greeting cards, toys, birds and animals from colored paper, and make amazing products from gauze.

Organizing work processes using only one method during the lesson can become a little boring for students. Therefore, the teacher will have to search for a new lesson and collect new materials. Currently, many beauties are created thanks to human labor. There are many websites where you can find these crafts and enjoy them with your students. There are more than a thousand types of simple paper flower making process. Searching for the best similar examples and showing them to students can increase the interest of more students in the class. This process helps students to develop their creative abilities, that is, not only to make what they see will motivate them to create

independently. The educational value of elementary technological education and technology lessons, teaching students manual labor, making them creative and mature people education, self-service, improvement of labor skills, practical in the process of training, it is to form skills and qualifications, to guide them to the profession, to educate students from an aesthetic point of view through application work, to create a foundation for students to become professional. Also, elementary school students use types of paper and various natural materials to create compositions and portraits in the direction of application. in the process of creation, their creative abilities develop further.

It is very important to guide students to choose the right profession. Because the chosen profession is related to the future of every person and affects the way of life. If a person enjoys his chosen profession or profession, he will be satisfied with his work. He will become a master of his profession, he will be noticed, he will find blessings. School plays an important role in choosing a profession. Some students are interested in physics, chemistry, biology, others in literature, history or law. For example, those interested in biology can become veterinarians or biologists in the future. Students interested in law can become lawyers, lawyers, prosecutors, and judges. Students interested in physics will become engineers or communicators. Students who are interested in mathematics can become economists, bankers, and accountants in the future, and students who are interested in foreign languages can work as translators, ambassadors, and guides. Previously, labor was considered a 2-3 level subject. Practical training was conducted using paper, pencil, eraser, and natural materials. Now this subject is called "Technology" and classes are taught by highly qualified teachers. In grades 5-9, students are trained in 3-4 professions and participate in production practice. The given theoretical knowledge is strengthened by practical lessons. The processes mentioned above have given effective results for large classes. In order to reach this process, it is necessary to create interest in technology lessons and organize effective lesson processes from the primary school age. It certainly depends on the professional skills and work experience of the pedagogue.

Elementary classes are taught to make various simple and easy items from different types of paper during technology classes. When organizing these processes, we should first thoroughly introduce them to work tools and thoroughly explain the functions and features of each work tool. In the process of completing the tasks given in the textbooks, students make things with their own hands, and in this process they develop skills. The first manifestations of the skills of work and creativity in young children are formed through this science. Elementary classes often use colored papers, felt-tip pens, plasticine, pencils, scissors, glue, and ruler in technology classes. When

using them, children will have to follow the rules of safety, conduct training in a condition that meets the requirements of sanitary hygiene. For example: be careful when using scissors, always keep the scissors in a closed case, when handing to a friend, hold three parts and pass with the back. In addition, when working with glue, work carefully and do not leak.

Work tools should always be stored in special containers. A number of tasks and requirements are set for students and teachers in technology classes. To these we can say:

Teacher's role:

1. Introduces the requirements for working in the labor room;
2. Teaches students the correct organization of the workplace in labor classes;
3. Introduces technical safety rules;
4. Types of practical work tools and rules for their use introduces. Work room requirements
 1. Access to the study room only with the permission of the teacher.
 2. Each student works only at his workplace. If you work as a team students are well aware of their responsibilities.
 3. The work starts only with the permission of the teacher Before starting work, prepare the work area and have the tools correct and handy.
 4. Placement: Right hand tools to the right, left hand put the one that is handled with on the left side, stabbing, cutting tools never put between two tools, always keep them in place, sharp side the other, turn the handle towards you. Don't play with instruments, they're toys it's not.
 5. Keep your workplace tidy during work hours.
 6. Do not use broken or broken tools.
 7. When using the tool, use it as instructed by the teacher.
 8. Store tools, use them correctly, in their proper place, and then dispose of them. clean it up.
 9. To make every detail higher quality, beautiful and orderly than the last time make an effort
 10. When you're done, quickly clean and tidy your work area.

Proper organization of the workplace:

The teacher writes a table on the table, right side scissors, glue brush, ruler, pencil, eraser places Glue to the front of the student, a box for scissors and a towel is placed. To the left of the student, interrupt during work colorful paper balls, paper balls and necessary materials will be placed. Sanitary and hygiene requirements: Special work aprons and sleeves are worn to prevent soiling of the student's clothes while working

at the desk. The use of work tools requires the orderly use of each tool or work tool, that is, using one work tool to put it in place and then grab the other. In this case, the student will be overwhelmed by the desktop. During work, the student may not touch his clothes, head, or face, if necessary, wipe his hand with a towel and then move his hand. After finishing the work, work tools and tools in their case or should put it in containers and place it in a bag or on a special shelf. Rules for proper sitting: Students must follow proper seating arrangements during work hours. While using any tool or working tool, one should not move the hands sharply, do not stand up, do not look back, do not turn to the side, do not speak to a friend. During work, it is necessary to keep the body straight, not to lean to one side, to place the legs correctly, to move the hands on the table, not to bring tools and tools close to the body, to sit properly at the work table. Then the student will not be tired or bored. In short, mentally preparing students for work means forming conscious and positive attitudes towards work that are appropriate for their age, forming interest in acquiring practical skills and abilities. working conditions require focus, activity, difficulties despite this, it allows to cultivate the habits of being able to finish the work that has been started, to develop the creative initiative of students

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